

FATIGUE LIFE EVALUATION OF SPAR CAP MATERIALS BY FOUR POINT BENDING TEST ON WIDTH-TAPERED SPECIMENS

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ABSTRACT

The presented research project focuses on an effective method to evaluate the fatigue strength of thick unidirectional laminates to be applied in spar caps. Therefore, a width-tapered bending specimen was developed for a four point loading set up. Static and fatigue loading was performed with the load ratio of $R=-1$. The complex stress state was investigated numerically with a finite element analysis. Finally, the concept was proven experimentally on specimens made of pultruded fibre rods. The fatigue behaviour of continuous tapered width by water jet cutting was compared to discrete tapering by rod-drop.

1 INTRODUCTION

Wings with a high aspect ratio for aircraft or wind turbine blades have a separated casting method [1, 2] as the usual structural design. The wing shell ensures the aerodynamic performance and bears the torsion. The inner spar structure covers the bending loads. The spar caps in a polymer fibre composite structure are thick unidirectional carbon or glass fibre layers which have to be tapered to the wing tip due to the decreasing bending moment. For a fast evaluation of the fatigue behaviour of new materials and / or new concepts of spar caps production a screening test was needed.

Therefore, a new test method was developed to evaluate the fatigue life of unidirectional composite materials of high tensile strength and stiffness. At tapered high loaded spar caps, combined normal and shear loading appears. Hence, a width-tapered specimen was numerically designed and fatigue loaded in a four point bending test with the load ratio of -1 . The specimen is symmetric to the centre line and the tapered parts are between the inner and outer clamping. This set up has the advantage of an easy load application by avoidance of failure in the clamping which often occurs at uniaxial tensile and compression loaded specimens of thick unidirectional laminates.

In terms of a new concept for spar cap design the use of pultruded fibre rods was evaluated as a new concept in a research project. In a pultrusion process a high fibre volume ratio of approximately 64% was achieved with carbon fibres and epoxy matrix. Additionally, a very good and controlled quality of impregnation and filament alignment was reached. Hence, the compression strength of the rod is at least 40% higher compared to conventional wet roving lay-up techniques. This can be raised up to nearly 2000 MPa compression strength which was already realized with HT-carbon-fibre rods [3, 4]. With respect to a packing density of the rods of about 85%, the average fibre volume ratio reaches about 55% which is a common number for roving wet lay-up techniques. However, the benefit in strength remains for the CF-rod-design named "spaghetti-technique".

For large volume and scale production it would be much more affordable if the rods would simply end when the cross section of the spar cap has to be reduced to the wing tip. With the developed tapered specimen geometry this was evaluated in four-point bending fatigue tests on specimens with different tapered width. One series of specimens was manufactured with continuous tapered width by

water jet cutting and the second series was discrete tapered by rod-drop in the measuring zone. The method, the experimental set up and the results are presented and discussed in this study.

2 NUMERICAL ANALYSIS

In dependence on [5] a four point bending tests specimen was designed. However, in contrast to this standard the width is not constant over the specimen length direction. The specific idea was to generate a complex stress state of superposed length and shear stress in the tapered region (Figure 1, position 3). The width decreases from 42mm at position 2 linearly to 30mm width at position 4. Hence, this results in a taper ratio of 1.4 on the length of 90mm. The specimen has a constant thickness of 8.2mm and is symmetric with respect to the x- and y-direction (s. Figure 2).

Figure 1: Geometry of the width tapered four point bending specimens.

The finite element analysis was done with ANSYS [6]. Due to the symmetry it is sufficient to model only a quarter of the specimen (s. Figure 2). 20 knots volume elements with a quadratic function for the field displacement calculation were used. The numbers of elements were 90 in x-direction and 10 in y-direction. In z-direction 16 elements were taken to consider stress gradients in the support and loading region. To reflect the right material properties a constitutive law for an orthotropic material with typical material constants for a CFRP was taken into the model.

Figure 2: FEM-model, due to symmetry only a quarter of the real geometry has to be modelled

Figure 3: Qualitative length strain – blue is compression and red is tensile strain

The strain in x-direction is shown qualitatively in figure 3. Blue colour depict compression and red colour tensile strain. Due to the load transfer the strain is locally slightly affected and enhanced. In figure 4 the shear strain is shown in the longitudinal x-z-middle section. As estimated from linear analytic approaches the shear stress increases in the neutral axis compared to the top and bottom of the specimen. The shear strain at the boundary area is shown in figure 6. As desired due to the width tapering there is a high increase of the shear strain in the centre of the tapered region.

Figure 4: Shear strain in the longitudinal x-z-middle section of the specimen

Figure 5: Shear strain in the boundary area.

To evaluate the stress state quantitatively with regard to the experiment the x-strain on top and bottom side and the shear stress in the neutral axis were plotted versus the width at the positions marked in figure 1. The virtual applied load is 4kN, hence, 2kN are applied on each load attachment. This affects a strain of 0.4% at the position 1 (green) in the middle of the specimen in between the load attachment points. This is in good accordance to the linear analytic approach. As expected the shear stress at this position is zero. At position 2 (blue) at the load attachment the compression strain is enhanced of about 10%. The tensile strain on the opposite site (bottom side) is less affected. Due to an anticlastic deformation the strain decreases and the shear stress increases to the free edge. However, the shear strain in the middle is much lower than according to linear theory (8,7MPa). At position 3 (red) the strain decreases in good accordance to the linear theory due to the decreasing bending moment. However, due to the tapering of the width the shear stress at the free edge increases to the highest value. This value is approximately twice as high as calculated according to the analytical approach (10,2MPa). Finally, at position 4 (black) there is the highest mean value of shear stress hence, there is the lowest cross sectional area. Nevertheless, the maximum value at the free edge is lower than at position 3. Hence, this position is the rated break point.

Figure 6: x-strain on top and bottom of the specimen vs. the relative width at different length positions (1-4: green, blue, red black) according to Figure 1.

Figure 7: Shear strain in the neutral axis of the specimen vs. the relative width at different length positions (1-4: green, blue, red black) according to Figure 1.

3 MATERIAL AND EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

3.1 Material and Test Samples

The carbon fibre rods were made of high tensile carbon fibres type HTS 5631, 12k, 800tex in a pultrusion process with an average fibre volume content of 64%. The diameter of the rods was 3mm. In a female moulding process 41 rods were bonded together by injection resin transfer moulding. A hexagonal rod arrangement was performed resulting in 3 layers (layout 14, 13, 14) with an effective thickness of 8,2mm. Two series of specimens were produced. One with discrete tapering by rod-drop (s. figure 8) on the left side and with continuous tapering by water jet cutting (s. figure 9) on the right side, hence later one named “asymmetric”. The second series was manufactured with continuous tapering on both sides and hence named “symmetric”. The epoxy resins were Hexion EPIKOTE™ Resin L20, EPIKURE™ Curing Agent 960 (“SL”) and EPIKOTE™ Resin L285, EPIKURE™ Curing Agent 287.

Figure 8: Discrete tapering by rod-drop

Figure 9: Continuous tapering by water jet cutting

3.2 Experimental setup static and fatigue

The rods were embedded (bonded) in steel cylinders and compression tested (s. figure 10). The mean value of the reached compression strength was about 1200MPa.

Figure 10: Compression test on CF-rod

Figure 11: Four point bending set up for tensile, compression and cyclic loading

A new apparatus for the four point bending test was designed as shown in figure 11. The distance of the outer supports can be adjusted at a distance from 100mm to 500mm. The inner load attachment can be adjusted between 50mm and 200mm. The apparatus is designed for a maximum load of 10kN. The bending specimen is pivot supported in cages. Thus, the specimen deflection is free. In x-direction an end-fixtue prevents the specimen to slip out. However, the shortening due to the deflection of the specimen is free. Therefore, in the cages the specimen is mounted on rollers. Additionally, the specimen is fixed in y-direction with screws. Finally, tensile compression and cyclic loading at different load ratios is possible. Especially the load ratio $R=-1$ was performed in the fatigue experiments.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

At first, flexural tests to failure were performed. The outer fibre strain was measured in the middle of the specimens with strain gauges. The flexural stress was calculated according to [5]. Specimens of the symmetric series with continuous tapered width show nearly linear stress strain behaviour till the total failure (s. figure 12). The maximum strain at fracture is 90% of the fracture strain of the carbon fibre rods. Firstly, cracks occur in the tapered region at a high load level short before the final global fracture. At the asymmetric bending test specimens the first crack appears at an outer fibre strain of 0.35% in the region tapered by rod-drop (like shown in figure 14 and 15). Successively, more and more cracks develop and the rods of the free edge region start more and more to delaminate till only the un-tapered rods in the centre take the load.

Figure 12: Flexural strength test on symmetric and asymmetric tapered specimens.

Further on, single step fatigue test were performed at 50% of the static strength nearly on the load level calculated in the FE analysis. The load ratio was $R=-1$. In figure 13 the normalized effective stiffness is plotted versus the number of load cycles. Again, the first crack appears in the region of discrete tapering by rod-drop at 10500 load cycles (s. Figure 14). Successively the rod starts to delaminate (s. Figure 15). Finally, the global stiffness decreases more than 30% and the test was stopped at 35000 load cycles. The continuous and symmetric tapered specimen shows no cracks up to this number of load cycles (s. figure 16) and start to degrade at 150000 load cycles. The first appearance of a crack is in the tapered region again as expected from the FE analysis (s. figure 17).

Figure 13: Flexural fatigue test on symmetric and asymmetric tapered specimens. Load ratio $R=-1$

Figure 14: Discrete tapering by rod-drop Figure 15: Continuous tapering by water jet cutting

Figure 16: Discrete tapering by rod-drop Figure 17: Continuous tapering by water jet cutting

In a second step, only the continuously tapered and symmetric specimens were investigated. In this test series the type of epoxy matrix which was filled in the interstitial of the rods in the infusion process and the post cure process was varied. The L20/SL epoxy system has the highest potential glass transition temperature. However, after a post cure at 60°C the fatigue performance was the weakest (s. figure 18). After a post cure at 130°C the fatigue performance was the best. The L285/H287 epoxy system is in between these values.

Figure 18: Flexural fatigue test on symmetric and asymmetric tapered specimens. Load ratio R=-1

The observed influence of the post cure process on the fatigue performance of epoxy resins is in good accordance to findings regarding the crack propagation rate as a function of the degree of cure [7]. However, in practice of large volume production, as e.g. in wind turbine blade industry, a high curing temperature causes high production costs. In addition, not all foam core materials withstand curing temperatures over 60°C or 80°C. Hence, it is necessary to find out where the limit is. L285/H287 is a standard epoxy system for the light weight aircraft industry and would be an affordable solution.

In this work a screening test was developed to evaluate the principle of tapered bending specimens and flexural loading. In a very extensive study [3] the potentials of pultruded CFRP-rods were investigated. Starting with the research for the best compression test, the authors reach values of approximately 2000MPa. Beside the test method itself, the preparation process of the CFRP-rods has a big influence on the maximum compression strength. In addition, design solutions for the use of pultruded rods in structural components were worked out [4]. Therefore, manufacturing techniques for arrangement and prefixing the rods were investigated. Furthermore, the pre-treatment of the rods surface in combination with different epoxy matrices were examined and classified in a transverse strength test. One important fact is the comparatively low transverse strength of the package of rods starting with 3.4MPa to 12MPa using only pure resin in the interstitial. If the infusion resin is loaded with short glass or carbon fibres, the transverse strength can be enhanced to 22MPa and hence, the inter fibre failure strength for CFRP of 20MPa to 30MPa is reached.

However, no inter fibre shear loading was investigated and the results of the flexural tests on the width tapered specimens reflect similarly a reduced inter rod shear strength compared to a normal UD-laminate.

In a further project spar structures with spar caps made of pultruded fibre rods were static and fatigue tested. The results were in good accordance to the flexural tests on the width tapered specimens and reveal the effectiveness of the presented test method.

5 CONCLUSION

A screening test for spar cap materials was developed. Therefore, a width tapered specimen for four point bending loading was designed. In addition, a test rig for flexural static and fatigue tests was developed especially feasible for alternating loads. Hence, cyclic fatigue tests with the load ratio of $R=-1$ were performed. A FE analysis reveals as rated break point the middle of the tapered region, as desired. A discrete width tapering by rod-drop and a continuously tapering by water jet cutting was investigated comparatively in static flexural strength and cyclic fatigue tests. In both cases the failure starts at the rated breakpoint. The discrete tapering shows the first failure due to delamination at the rod drop both at static and fatigue loading. The fatigue life of the continuous tapered specimen is one order of magnitude higher than the discrete tapering. In addition, the fatigue performance of different epoxy systems and the effect of post cure were investigated successfully. Finally, an effective screening test for the fatigue life of thick laminates, as spar cap materials was developed and successful evaluated.

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